

THE ROLE OF INTONATION IN SPEECH AND ARTISTIC SPEECH

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Abstract: It is known that phonostylistics is a new direction that emerged between the sciences of phonetics and stylistics in the further development of linguistics. Stylistic features of speech sounds in phonostylistics. Also, supersegmental phonetic means: intonation, pause, and stress, which express connotative meaning, are studied. Intonation is a supersegmental element that serves to express the syntactic meanings and emotional-expressive colors of speech, the rhythmic-melodic side, and the high-low voice. This article discusses the level of connotative meaning expression of intonation.

Keywords: phonostylistics, intonation, pause, stress, rhythmic-melodic, tempo of speech, timbre of speech, logical accent, emphatic accent, emotional - expressiveness.

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Descriptive phonetics deals with speech sounds, their formation, types, phonetic phenomena, such as syllables, intonation, pauses and their characteristics. The recorded events in the process of speech communication are combined into a single system and create a speech act. Therefore, in the interpretation and research of such phenomena, while studying them separately, it is necessary to assume that they are phenomena that require each other, in other words, that one cannot live without the other. [1, 24-28]

Intonation is one of the supersegmental phonetic means, which is defined as "the rhythmic-melodic side, high-low, tone of the voice that serves to express the syntactic meanings and expressive-emotional colors of the speech." [5'45] In linguistics, the second name of intonation is intonema, and the name of the field dealing with it is intology [2,23].

Intonation issues in European and US linguistics are covered in the scientific works of such linguists as: Antonova D.N, Artyomov Z.A, Barishnikova K, Brizgunova E.A, Zlatouyetova L.V, Kankter L.A, Machkova P.A, Mukhanov N.A, Peshkovskiy M, Svetazarova N.D, Tosouyev G.P, Trubetskoy V.A. In Uzbek linguistics, comments about intonation were made by A. Ghulomov, A. Abduazizov, A. Abdullayev, B. Yoldoshev, H. Yoldosheva, S. Karimov, J. Mamatov, A. Mahmudov, E. Qilichev, It can be found in the works of such linguists as G. Yakshayeva, B. Orinboyev, R. Kongurov, A. Haydarov, I. Khojialiyeu, M. Mirtojiiyev.

According to the above-mentioned scientists, intonation is the fact that each of the factors such as logical emphasis, emphatic emphasis, and pause cannot perform

an independent task on its own, and their sum is the intonation of the whole and the pronounced part of the speech. It is necessary to think about the speed of speech, tone of speech, pauses in the sentence. Intonation is found in all speech styles. The level of connotative meaning expression of intonation is strong in all speech styles, except for the scientific style. Intonation in oral speech is carried out by means of punctuation marks in written speech. Intonation performs different functions in a sentence. In particular, it represents the type of sentence, connection between its components, modality, emotional color, and additional meanings expressed in the sentence, such as counting, contrasting, contrasting. "In scientific sources", writes linguist S. Karimov, there is a concept of tact intonation. In the expression of emotional-expressiveness, intonation has a special character, it is the main and characteristic sign of any sentence. Emotionality is also determined by the speed of speech. For this reason, interrogative sentences are pronounced in a continuous tone compared to demonstrative sentences. For

example: Why should it worry you?

What's the good of doing that?

How about phoning them?

Separated sentence fragments, exclamations, introductory words are separated by tone in oral speech, and written by appropriate punctuation marks in written speech.

For example: Really! Well you must get him.

In this example, the introductory word Really is separated by an exclamation mark in writing, but in spoken speech it is pronounced with intonation.

will rain! - Perhaps, it
The

introductory word "perhaps" in the example is separated by a comma in writing, and pronounced with intonation in oral speech. The emotional aspect of intonation mainly expresses a stylistic meaning. Intonation serves as an important phonostylistic means in giving a certain stylistic color to the speaker's speech. If the stylistic meaning is expressed, then it is natural that the connotative (additional) meaning is expressed. Such connotative meanings are indifference, coldness, indifference, determination, pleading, and so on. In interrogative sentences, the low tone mainly expresses connotative meanings such as seriousness, responsibility, correct assessment of the situation [4, 69-72]. We

will focus on the analysis of the following examples. a) When

expressing the situation: Pete plays

football very well. - Petya fudbolni jud yaxshi o'ynaydi. During the

pronunciation of this sentence, the voice goes down and connotative meanings

such as satisfaction, pleasure, joy are expressed. b) When giving

the command: Go out! – Tashqarga chiq!
Pronounced in the tone of command, "additional" meanings such as command, hitting, determination appear in this sentence.
c) In general interrogative sentences: Do you mind my opening the window? – Derazani ochishga qarshi emasiz?

In this sentence, along with the content of the question, it can be seen that "additional" meanings such as "please", "beg", "compliment" are expressed. d) Feeling - excitement in sentences:

What a fine day! – Qanday ajoyib kun!

In this sentence, connotative meanings such as attention, joy, pleasure, and surprise are expressed. The analysis of the above sentences shows that different qualities of the speaker are expressed by the change of intonation, that is, the sentences are separated from each other and the speaker shows a pragmatic attitude to the opinion he expressed. Intonation plays an important role not only in speech and artistic speech styles, but also in poetry. Intonation is of great importance in the pronunciation of the lines of the poem, the poetic works are based on rhyme, and the poem is meaningless and dull when read without intonation.

Summary. Observations show that speech cannot be formed without intonation. It is difficult to imagine any phonetic phenomenon without intonation, regardless of the stylistic function. Intonation is considered an important phonostylistic means in giving a certain stylistic color to the speaker's speech. Expression of connotative meaning through intonation is stronger than other language units. Intonation and its components: The simultaneous use of pauses and accents in speech expresses a strong connotative meaning.

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